

Code:

Age: Sex:

1.(A) I feel tense or nervous.	Almost all day	Most of the day	From time to time	Never
2.(D) I still enjoy the same things as always.	Just like before	Not as much as before	Only a little	Not at all
3.(A) I feel a kind of fear, as if something bad were going to happen.	Completely, and it's very strong	Yes, but it's not very strong	A little, but I'm not worried	Not at all
4.(D) I can laugh and see the funny side of things.	As always Currently	somewhat less Currently,	Much less	Currently, not at all
5.(A) My head is full of worries.	Almost all day	Most of the day	From time to time	Never
6.(D) I feel happy.	Most of the day	On some occasions	Very rarely	Never
7. (A) I can remain seated, calm and relaxed.	Always	Often	Rarely	Never
8. (D) I feel slow and clumsy.	Most of the day	Often	Sometimes	Never
9. (A) I experience an unpleasant feeling of nervousness and emptiness in my stomach.	Never	Only on certain occasions	Often	Very often
10.(D) I have lost interest in my personal appearance.	Completely	I don't take care of myself as I should.	I may not be taking care of myself as I should.	I take care of myself just as I always have.
11.(A) I feel restless, as if I cannot stop moving.	A lot	Quite	Not much	Not at all
12. (D) I look forward to things with excitement.	As always	Slightly less than before.	Much less than before	Not at all
13. (A) I suddenly experience a feeling of anxiety or fear.	Muy frecuente	Quite often.	Not very often	Not at all
14. (D) I am able to enjoy a good book, radio or television programme..	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Almost never
TOTAL SCORE	ANXIETY			
	DEPRESSION			

Scoring:

Anxiety 0 -7: Normal 8-10: Borderline abnormal 11-21: Abnormal (case)

Depression 0 -7: Normal 8-10: Borderline abnormal 11-21: Abnormal (case)